

Parametric Study on Ultimate Bearing Capacity of CFST Arch Bridge

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

In this study a four-leg lattice structure CFST arch bridge is analyzed using finite element software (ANSYS) to predict the ultimate bearing capacity considering several parameters (slenderness ratio, steel content, steel type, and concrete type) under two influencing factors initial stress and geometric defects. There is an inverse relation found between the existence of the initial stress and ultimate bearing capacity and ultimately the overall stiffness of the structure has been reduced during non-linear stage. Larger the slenderness ratio, the greater the influence on the ultimate stability bearing capacity of with initial stresses and geometric defects. According to the ultimate bearing capacity coefficient under different steel content ratios, it can be known that the greater the steel content higher the bearing capacity coefficient. The increment rate of the ultimate bearing capacity coefficient is between 0 and 18%. The comparison of the ultimate bearing capacity coefficients under the four steel types shows that compared with Q235, the other three steel types the ultimate bearing capacity coefficient is 12%-24%. However, there relatively small influence of the two concrete grades C60 and C55 on the ultimate bearing capacity of the CFST arch bridge. The effect of initial defects in in-plane as better than the initial defects out-of-plan on ultimate bearing capacity CFST arch bridge. A comprehensive consideration of influence of the initial stress and the initial out-of-plane defects are considered simultaneously. The analysis results show that the amplitude of geometric defects is controlled within $L/5000$, and the initial stress is controlled within 0.4 within a reasonable range.

Keywords: FINITE ELEMENT METHOD; ANSYS; CONCRETE FILLED STEEL TUBE ARCH BRIDGE; PARAMETRIC ANALYSIS.

1 Introduction and background

CFST arch bridges are elegant structures with an architectural perspective and efficient in load bearing capacity over a long span, in recent years, with the rapid development, CFST arch bridges have gradually become one of the preferred structural forms. In terms of structural system. Figure 1 shows the three commonly used structural forms' according to the cross-sectional situation, the CFST arch rib. cross-section forms mainly include single-limb, double-limb dumbbell, and four-limb lattice configuration ^[1].

Figure 1 Schematic diagram of arch bridges of three structural systems

Arch rib axis may be possibly deviate from the original design linearity during the production, transportation, installation and bridge work stages of the arch bridge. When the arch rib deviates from the plane, it will cause the arch rib to tilt out of the plane ^[2]. When the arch rib is deviated in-plane, the axial force will produce eccentricity. Therefore, the initial defect affects the ultimate bearing capacity when the span of the CFST arch bridge is not large, the initial geometry is lacking the sinking has little effect on the ultimate bearing capacity of the arch bridge. Therefore, for the design of the small span CFST arch bridge, it is often the impact of initial defects is not considered ^[3]. However, when the bridge span is relatively large, a small initial defect will have a great impact on the arch rib, such as a bending moment that tilts out of the plane; or axial force a large eccentricity is produced, which makes the cross-section of the arch rib uneven and reduces the ultimate bearing capacity of the structure. When the initial defect is too large, it may directly lead to structural damage ^[4]. In order to be able to accurately analyze for the ultimate bearing capacity of the arch structure, the influence of initial geometric defects on the concrete-filled steel tube arch bridge must be considered ^[5].

2 literature review

Scholars have done research on the ultimate bearing capacity of CFST arch bridge considering different aspects. Among them, Jinliang Hu ^[6] studied the initial defect of the arch bridge he considered material and geometric non-linear double factors with defects of arch axis deviation and steel yield stress. Hai-Bang Ly ^[7] predicted the initial stress and initial defects of arch structure by using hybrid artificial intelligence (AI) approaches, such as an adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system and two ANFISs optimized by metaheuristic techniques. Silin Chen ^[8] studied CFST arch trusses with initial imperfections nonlinear analysis formwork with the reliability analysis of CFST truss with random imperfections based on on-site measurement data and Monte-Carlo (MC) simulations and he proposed reliabilities and related system resistance factors in regards to random initial imperfections. Dadeppo and Schmidt (1986) ^[9] analyzed the problem of large deformation and ultimate bearing capacity of arch structure. Austin ^[10] when the arch structure is under symmetrical load the problem of in-plane elastic buckling is studied and analyzed. Komatsu and Shinke ^[11] are the arch structure under the action of residual stress has been subjected to the ultimate strength analysis considering nonlinearity under uniform load, and a simple calculation formula for ultimate bearing capacity is given. Wang Ji ^[12] studied stability analysis of long-span CFST arch bridge, he concluded that the influence of geometrical nonlinearity and material nonlinearity must be considered at the same time. Timoshenko ^[13] analyzed the oblate arch and its ultimate bearing capacity of the structure under the action of vertical load analyzed and calculated different boundaries and predicted ultimate bearing capacity of the arch structure under the different conditions, and a simplified

formula is given. 1990s. Zhuang ^[14] studied initial Stress on the In-plane Ultimate Bearing Capacity of CFST Arch Bridges results showed that the influence of the initial stress of steel tube on the value of in plane ultimate bearing capacity was not obvious, while the effect on the deformation of arch structure was great and the arch structure displayed more plastic property because of the presence of the initial stress in steel tube.

2-1 Brief analysis of literature review

Researchers have done research on the ultimate bearing capacity CFST arch structures. However, there are few researches on the ultimate bearing capacity of CFST arch bridges, and there is lack of research. Researcher has studied the effect of initial stress on the ultimate bearing capacity of the concrete-filled steel tube arch bridge and summarized under the influence of the initial stress the calculation formula of the bearing capacity, but the research result is only the in-plane limit stability, and does not involve the out-of-plane limit stable. There are many studies on the influence of initial stress on the ultimate bearing capacity of CFST members, but it is less research on the structural level. Influence of initial geometric defects on ultimate bearing capacity of CFST arch bridge there are few studies. Therefore, the ultimate bearing capacity of concrete-filled steel tube arch bridges with initial stress and initial geometric defects analysis is required.

3-1 Analysis of the influence of initial stress on the ultimate bearing capacity of CFST arch bridge

In this research concrete-filled steel tube arch bridge under construction-Matan Hongshui River Bridge Ningbo city china is used for analysis.

The basic information is as follows:

Span layout of the main bridge is $L=329\text{m}$ and 327m long. The total width of the bridge deck is 49.5m , which is set according to two bridges. The total width of the single bridge deck is 31.2m , and the main bridge of the single bridge is horizontal. The section layout is: 3.2m (boom and inspection road) + 0.4m (anti-collision guardrail) + 18.4m (carriageway and Hard shoulder) + 0.4 (anti-collision guardrail) + 3.2m (boom and maintenance road). The calculated span of the main arch rib is 328m , the height of the vector is 70m , the ratio of the vector to the length is $1/3$, $m=1.13$. There are two arch ribs in a single bridge, and the distance between the center of the bridge is 24.7m . The upper and lower chords have a diameter of 1100mm and a wall thickness of $21\sim 30\text{mm}$. C55 micro-expansion concrete is poured into the tube; The diameter of the web rod steel tube is 610mm , and the wall thickness is 14mm ; the transverse tube diameter is 799mm , and the wall thickness is 18mm . C90 steel grit concrete is poured into the anchor tube at the point anchor head.

3-2 Finite element modelling of CFST arch bridge:

Large-scale finite element analysis software ANSYS is used to carry out the modeling analysis of the Matan Hongshui River Bridge. Influence of different parameters on the influence of the ultimate bearing capacity of the concrete-filled steel tube arch bridge with initial stress is analyzed. The main parameters considered are

slenderness ratio, steel material type, concrete type, steel content, etc.

A modeling analysis of a CFST arch bridge with four limbs under construction is carried out. Example model span is 329m, the steel content is 0.10, and the steel tube of 1100 ×30mm is used, and the material used: Q345 steel and concrete model is C55 and build erected model is shown in Figure 2, and the section of a single chord (customized section) is shown.

Figure 2 CFST Arch bridge finite element model

Figure 3 Sectional view of a single chord

3-2-1 Material properties

The nominal tube thickness is 8mm, 10 mm, 12mm, 14mm and 16mm. Material properties of steel for this section of study were used with the specification (GB 50017-2003)^[15].

Three different grades of concrete strengths, C50, C55, and C60 were used for this parametric study. concrete elastic modulus and the average cubic strength (f_{cu}) were taken from (GB 50010-2010) ^[16]

Table 1. Concrete properties (Yong’s modulus, compressive strength)

Concrete strength grade	Young ‘s modulus E_c (MPa)	Compressive strength f_{cu} (MPa)
C50	26690	42
C55	29380	54
C60	38070	68

3-2-2 Material modeling

ANSYS creates each material as an individual part, and then different parts are assembled using instances option provided in ANSYS.

A. Steel tube

In the said model, an elastic-perfectly plastic model is modeled to simulate the steel tube in ABAQUS 6.13. The Poisson's ratio is taken as 0.3.

B. Concrete core

The Drucker Prager plasticity model available in ANSYS was adopted for specimens to describe the plastic stress strain behavior of the confined concrete. The Poisson's ratio is taken as 0.2.

3-3 Analysis of the influence of initial stress on ultimate bearing capacity of concrete-filled steel tube arch bridge

Before the steel tube and the core concrete form a combined structure, the thin-walled steel tube must bear its own weight and the core concrete in the tube weight, there is a stress of σ_0 in the steel tube, which is called the initial stress. The ratio of the initial stress σ_0 to the yield strength f_y of the steel, the value of β is represented by [17].

$$B = \sigma / f_y$$

Abbreviated as the initial stress degree, where f_y represents the yield stress of the steel.

3.3.1 Influence coefficient of ultimate bearing capacity of concrete-filled steel tube arch bridge

In order to facilitate the analysis of the influence of the initial stress of the steel tube on the ultimate bearing capacity of the arch bridge, the ultimate bearing capacity is defined the influence coefficient k_p of, its expression is [18]:

$$K_p = Y_p / Y_0$$

In the formula, Y_p and Y_0 are the series of ultimate bearing capacity of the concrete-filled steel tube arch bridge considering the effect of the initial stress of the steel tube.

3.3.2 Influence of initial stress on ultimate bearing capacity of concrete-filled steel tube arch bridge

The CFST arch bridge with a steel tube wall thickness of 28mm (outer diameter of 0.7m) was made under different initial stresses. The ultimate bearing capacity analysis, the ultimate bearing capacity coefficient under different initial stress degrees (Table 2) and displacement graph (Figure 4), and graph of ultimate bearing capacity coefficient changing with initial stress (Figure 5) It can be seen that with the increase of the initial stress, the ultimate bearing capacity coefficient of the concrete-filled steel tube arch bridge is approximately a straight line decline.

Table 2 Table of calculation results under different initial stress degrees

Initial stress	Initial stress (MPa)	Ultimate bearing capacity factor	displacement at mid-span (m)
0	0	4.227	0.727
0.1	35.4	3.972	0.7115
0.2	70	3.897	0.732
0.3	104.6	3.757	0.742

0.4	146	3.559	0.732
0.5	169.5	3.426	0.743
0.6	211	3.234	0.746
0.7	231.6	3.107	0.804
0.8	271	2.960	0.832

Figure 4 Load-displacement curve diagram under different initial stress

Figure 5 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficient under different initial stress

3-4 The effect of slenderness ratio

The wall thickness of the steel tube is 28mm, and the outer diameter is 1100-1300mm with an interval of 95mm, the ultimate bearing capacity system of CFST arch bridges with different slenderness ratios is obtained through analysis and calculated the influence coefficient p_k of the number and ultimate bearing capacity varies with the initial stress degree. It can be seen from Figure 7 the greater the slenderness ratio, the ultimate bearing capacity coefficient is high under the same initial stress. The reasons for this phenomenon are: For the CFST arch bridge with the larger slenderness ratio, under the same initial stress of the steel tube, the arch ribs will produce the initial deformation, the greater the initial deformation of the concrete in the tube, which will affect the ultimate bearing capacity of the concrete-filled steel tube arch bridge will be bigger. Among them, the slenderness ratio is changed by changing the section radius, and the yield strength of the steel is taken as 355MP.

Table 3 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficients under different slenderness ratios

Initial stress	Slenderness ratio	1000mm	1100mm	1200mm	1300mm	1400mm
0	0	3.39	3.86	4.10	4.64	4.91
0.1	35.5	3.21	3.75	3.89	4.51	4.80
0.2	69.5	3.10	3.57	3.81	4.37	4.71
0.3	104.5	2.89	3.44	3.69	4.23	4.56
0.4	139	2.69	3.25	3.58	4.11	4.49
0.5	173.5	2.57	2.97	3.50	3.94	4.07
0.6	208	2.37	2.72	3.32	3.85	4.01
0.7	242.5	2.18	2.51	3.23	3.62	3.86

Figure 6 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficient under different slenderness ratio

Figure 7 The influence coefficient of ultimate bearing capacity under different slenderness ratio

3-5 The influence of steel content

Ultimate bearing capacity of the concrete-filled steel tube arch bridge with initial stress is affected by different steel content. Different steel content results of the influence of the ratio on the ultimate bearing capacity of the concrete-filled steel tube arch bridge with initial stress are shown in Figure 6. When the cross-sectional area is constant, with the increase of the steel content, the ultimate bearing capacity coefficient of the CFST arch bridge it also increases, because the greater the steel content, the greater the radial restraint effect of the steel tube on the core concrete, and the core concrete can bear more internal forces. From the influence of different steel content on the ultimate bearing capacity coefficient in Figure 8, the energy It can be seen that when the initial stress is unchanged, the lower the steel content, the greater the value of the influence coefficient p_k , the steel content of the section is small, the total load that the steel can withstand is smaller, and when the initial stress is the same.

Table 4 Steel tube wall thickness under different steel content

Initial stress	size	7%	8%	9%	10%	11%	12%
0	0	3.65	3.84	4.17	4.28	4.43	4.40
0.1	35.5	3.55	3.80	3.85	4.17	4.28	4.31
0.2	69.5	3.47	3.78	3.81	3.90	3.88	4.23
0.3	104.5	3.37	3.64	3.77	3.83	3.76	3.97
0.4	139	3.22	3.53	3.62	3.71	3.62	3.87
0.5	173.5	3.13	3.41	3.43	3.56	3.43	3.74
0.6	208	3.02	3.25	3.31	3.44	3.44	3.57
0.7	242.5	2.86	3.16	3.10	3.24	3.21	3.38
0.8	277	2.62	2.90	2.81	2.89	2.89	2.89

Table 5 The growth rate of ultimate bearing capacity coefficient under different steel content ratio compared with 7% steel content ratio (%)

Initial stress	size	8%	9%	10%	11%	12%
0	0	6.5	9.4	10.4	14.3	16.2
0.1	35.5	3.9	8.3	8.3	12.2	14.3
0.2	69.5	4.6	7.6	10.2	11.1	17.4
0.3	104.5	3.9	5.6	7.2	10.2	13.4
0.4	139	2.6	3.3	6.1	9.1	12.6
0.5	173.5	4.1	3.4	5.0	7.9	11.7
0.6	208	2.4	1.9	3.5	5.4	8.8
0.7	242.5	4.4	2.4	3.8	4.8	7.3
0.8	277	-1.4	1.8	2.4	2.8	6.2

Figure 8 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficient under different steel content ratios

Figure 9 The influence coefficient of ultimate bearing capacity under different steel content

3-6 Influence of steel type

The ultimate bearing capacity coefficient of CFST arch bridge changes with different initial stress degrees when only the steel type of the cross-section is changed. The results show that the higher the steel strength, the higher the ultimate bearing capacity coefficient of the concrete-filled steel tube arch bridge. From Figure 9, it can be seen that the poles of the four steel models (Q235, Q345, Q390, Q420) the influence coefficient p_k of limited bearing capacity varies with the degree of initial stress. The greater the yield strength of the steel, the greater the initial stress at the same time, the initial stress has greater influence on the ultimate bearing capacity influence coefficient p_k , but the influence is not very large. Because the yield strength is different, but the elastic modulus takes the same value. Given in Table 4-6 the growth rate of Q420, Q390, and Q345 steel models compared to Q235.

Table 6 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficients under different steel types

Initial Strength	Size	Q235	Q345	Increase rate %	Q390	Increase rate %	Q420	Increase rate %
0	0	4.66	5.2	16.5	5.26	23.0	6.32	35.1
0.1	35.5	4.52	4.89	16.4	5.32	21.8	6.41	36.3
0.2	69.5	4.45	4.76	16.4	5.17	21.2	6.33	35.2
0.3	104.5	4.32	4.65	17.3	4.79	20.6	6.17	35.5
0.4	139	4.26	4.59	13.2	4.68	17.9	5.79	32.7
0.5	173.5	4.12	4.50	13.1	4.61	17.4	5.61	30.6
0.6	208	3.89	4.32	9.7	4.44	13.3	5.55	26.4
0.7	242.5	3.78	4.22	8.4	4.27	11.5	5.43	23.0

Figure 10 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficients under different steel types

Figure 11 the influence coefficient of ultimate bearing capacity under different steel types

3-7 Influence of concrete grade

The ultimate bearing capacity coefficients under different concrete grades are shown in Table 7 below. As shown in Figure 12, It can be seen from the figure that the higher the concrete strength, the higher the ultimate bearing capacity coefficient of the CFST arch bridge. The following figure 13 is the influence coefficient p_k of the ultimate bearing capacity of the three concrete grades (C50, C55, C60). From the result we can see the higher the strength of the concrete grade, the greater the ultimate bearing capacity coefficient, but the stronger the concrete when the degree of difference is not very large, the difference in the coefficient of influence on the ultimate bearing capacity is not very large. Different concrete grades have a great impact on the concrete-filled steel tube arch bridge with initial stress. The influence of the limited bearing capacity is not obvious. The following table 7 shows the comparison of C60 and C55 concrete grades with C50 the ultimate bearing capacity coefficient growth rate below.

Table 7 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficients under different concrete grades

Initial stress	size	C50	C55	Growth rate (%)	C60	Growth rate (%)
0.0	0	5.12	5.21	3.8	5.29	9.0
0.1	35.5	4.89	4.89	3.3	5.21	7.8
0.2	69.5	4.81	4.81	4.6	5.17	6.7
0.3	104.5	4.72	4.69	5.1	4.95	6.8
0.4	139	4.51	4.62	5.3	4.81	9.6
0.5	173.5	4.31	4.51	5.4	4.72	9.8
0.6	208	4.22	4.32	3.8	4.54	6.1
0.7	242.5	3.89	4.21	2.7	4.36	8.5
0.8	0	3.81	3.99	4.2	4.29	9.3

Figure 12 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficients under different concrete grades

Figure 13 The influence coefficient of ultimate bearing capacity under different concrete grades

3-8 Analysis of influence of nonlinearity on ultimate bearing capacity of concrete-filled steel tubular arch bridge

For the elastic stability of the CFST arch bridge structure, only the material nonlinearity and the dual nonlinearity are considered under the load-bearing capacity, the first type of instability is the buckling mode analysis under the calculated elastic condition; When only material nonlinearity and dual nonlinearity are considered, take 12 times the weight of the arch rib as the load stepwise increase Load it on the structure for analysis until the structure does not converge. The analysis results are shown in Figure 4-13, 4-14, 4-15, as shown in Table 3-8.

1
DISPLACEMENT
STEP=1
SUB =1
FACT=5.84965
DMX =1.00223

ANSYS
R15.0
DEC 15 2020
08:45:13

Figure 14 The A class of instability results

2
DISPLACEMENT
STEP=1
SUB =10
TIME=.459863
DMX =.993871

ANSYS
R15.05.C
DEC 15 2020
09:15:34

Figure 15 The result of considering only the material nonlinearity

3
DISPLACEMENT
STEP=1
SUB =12
TIME=.41147
DMX =.726177

ANSYS
R15.0
DEC 15 2020
12:45:38

Figure 16 The result of considering the double nonlinearity

Table 8 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficients under three calculation theories

Working condition	Stability factor
A class of stability	6.95
B class of stability	Only consider material nonlinearities
	Consider double nonlinearity
	5.48
	4.23

It can be seen from the comparison table that the CFST arch bridge obtained by elastic stability has the largest

stability coefficient is 6.95; when analyzing the second-class stability, if only the material nonlinearity is considered, the stability coefficient is 5.48, the same type of stability is reduced by 31.22%; if the effects of double nonlinearity are also considered, the stability fixed coefficient is 4.23, which is the smallest. Compared with the stability of the same type, it drops by 30.43%. The analysis results show that these three factors affect the ultimate bearing capacity of the CFST arch bridge. Material nonlinearity has a more obvious influence on the ultimate bearing capacity of arch bridges. Geometric nonlinearity is compared with material nonlinearity.

4-The influence of initial defects on the bearing capacity of concrete-filled steel tube arch bridges

4-1 Classification of initial geometric defects:

The overall initial geometric defects of the concrete-filled steel tube arch bridge exist in the whole bridge, and most scholars choose the same defect Trap method for analysis. The consistent defect method refers to the characteristic value of the long-span arch bridge in the elastic range buckling analysis, the buckling mode of the arch bridge is obtained, and this mode is used as the layout method for imposing initial geometric defects. The formula is used to simulate the initial geometric defects. This is because the buckling shape is the potential displacement trend of the arch structure, such as the distribution position of the initial geometric defects of the concrete-filled steel tube arch bridge just coincides with the buckling shape, and the initial geometric defects will have a very adverse effect on the ultimate bearing capacity of the arch structure.

Figure 17 Overall defect of Arch Structure

Figure 18 Partial defects of Arch Structure

4-2 Distribution and size of initial defects

a) The size of the initial defect

The initial defect size takes four cases: $L/5000$, $L/4000$, $L/3000$, $L/2000$, where L is the net span, in cm, for the model used in this paper, the net span is 327m, and the amplitude is as shown in the following Table 9, the defect amplitude indicates the distance of the arch rib node from the design node, and the coordinate of the node is changed in the model to simulate the geometric structure with the initial geometric defect.

Table 9 The magnitude of initial geometric defects

Amplitude	0	L/5000	L/4000	L/3000	L/2000
size (cm)	0	5.88	9.0	10.3	15.5

b) Distribution method

According to the actual construction situation, several working conditions as shown in Figure 19 are drawn up, among which A1, B1, C1 Initial geometric defects distributed vertically (in-plane); A2, B2, C2 are distributed laterally (out-of-plane).

Figure 19 Illustration of geometric defects outside and inside the plane

a) The effect of out-of-plane initial defects

As shown in the figure above, A2, B2, and C2 are initial geometric defects distributed laterally (out-of-plane). The following table 10 is the ultimate bearing capacity coefficient in the case of three out-of-plane geometric defects.

Table 10 The ultimate bearing capacity coefficients in the case of three out-of-plane geometric defects

Defect amplitude (cm)	A2	B2	C2
0	4.12	4.10	4.10
5.88	3.78	3.78	3.78
9.0	3.90	3.75	3.73
10.3	3.73	3.72	3.67
15.5	3.69	3.62	3.64

Figure 20 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficient Under different working conditions

It can be seen from the result graph that under the initial in-plane defect, when the defect amplitude is not greater than L/5000 at the same time, the ultimate bearing capacity coefficients of the three defective conditions are basically the same, and the ultimate bearing capacity under the three conditions the force decreases with the increase of the geometric defect amplitude. By comparing the ultimate bearing capacity coefficients under the same geometric defect amplitude in the corresponding working conditions in and out of the plane now, the initial geometric defects in the plane have a greater impact on the ultimate bearing capacity than the initial geometric defects outside the plane.

Consider the effects of initial stress and initial out-of-plane defects

The results of no defects under A2 working condition are shown in Table 11 below.

Table 11 No-defect ultimate bearing capacity coefficient under A2 working condition

Initial stress	Initial stress value (MPa)	Ultimate bearing capacity factor	Mid-span sinking value	Mid-span lateral offset
0	0	5.21	-1.831	0
0.1	35.5	4.89	-1.825	0
0.2	69.5	4.81	-1.841	0
0.3	104.5	4.79	-1.834	0
0.4	139	4.66	-1.829	0
0.5	173.5	4.521	-1.849	0
0.6	208	4.39	-1.831	0
0.7	242.5	4.22	-1.810	0
0.8	0	3.99	-1.817	0

The results of L/5000 geometric defects under A2 working condition are shown in Table 12 below.

Table 12 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficient under L/5000/4000/3000/2000 geometric defect amplitude under A2 working condition

Initial stress	Initial stress value (MPa)				Ultimate bearing capacity factor				Mid-span sinking value				Mid-span lateral offset				
	L/5000/4000/3000/2000	L/2000	L/3000	L/4000	L/5000	L/2000	L/3000	L/4000	L/5000	L/2000	L/3000	L/4000	L/5000	L/2000	L/3000	L/4000	L/5000
0	0	0	0	0	0	3.68	3.74	3.88	3.79	0.641	-0.65	-0.689	-0.647	-0.47	-0.42	0.457	-0.306
0.1	34.5	34.5	34.5	34.5	34.5	3.51	3.56	3.6	3.6	0.596	-0.6	-0.609	-0.602	-0.46	-0.373	-0.39	-0.333
0.2	69	69	69	69	69	3.31	3.36	3.41	3.41	0.565	-0.56	-0.581	-0.562	-0.56	-0.427	-0.497	-0.338
0.3	103.5	103.5	103.5	103.5	103.5	3.13	3.31	3.31	3.31	0.531	-0.56	-0.543	-0.534	-0.58	0.446	0.303	0.217
0.4	138	138	138	138	138	2.94	3.46	2.99	3.47	0.524	-0.71	-0.509	-0.711	-0.76	-0.233	-0.556	-0.195
0.5	172.5	172.5	172.5	172.5	172.5	2.7	2.74	2.93	2.79	0.485	-0.5	-0.608	-0.522	-0.73	-0.726	0.972	-0.782
0.6	207	207	207	207	207	2.51	2.51	2.55	3.12	0.538	-0.48	-0.526	-0.733	-1.12	-0.723	-0.951	-0.228
0.7	241.5	241.5	241.5	241.5	241.5	2.26	2.3	2.3	2.35	0.485	-0.58	-0.485	-0.533	-0.88	-1.359	-0.766	-0.98
0.8	276	276	276	276	276	2.07	2.08	2.17	2.17	0.536	-0.5	-0.606	-0.599	-1.13	-0.856	1.313	1.276

The results without defects under B2 working condition are shown in Table 13 below.

Table 13 Calculation results under B2 working condition without defects

Initial stress	Initial stress value (MPa)	Ultimate bearing capacity factor	Mid-span sinking value	Mid-span lateral offset
0	0	5.32	-1.821	0
0.1	35.5	4.86	-1.827	0
0.2	69.5	4.77	-1.839	0
0.3	104.5	4.70	-1.837	0
0.4	139	4.64	-1.820	0
0.5	173.5	4.51	-1.835	0
0.6	208	4.41	-1.839	0
0.7	242.5	4.31	-1.826	0
0.8	0	3.89	-1.810	0

The results of L/5000 geometric defects under B2 working condition are shown in Table 14 below.

Table 14 Calculation results under L/5000/4000/3000/2000 geometric defect amplitude under B2 working condition

Initial stress L/5000/4000/3000/2000	Initial stress value (MPa)				Ultimate bearing capacity factor				Mid-span sinking value				Mid-span lateral offset			
	L/2000	L/3000	L/4000	L/5000	L/2000	L/3000	L/4000	L/5000	L/2000	L/3000	L/4000	L/5000	L/2000	L/3000	L/4000	L/5000
0	0	0	0	0	3.63	3.73	3.74	3.79	-0.598	-0.62	-0.619	-0.634	-0.34	-0.374	-0.273	-0.305
0.1	34.5	34.5	34.5	34.5	3.47	3.55	3.55	3.6	-0.558	-0.58	-0.57	-0.586	-0.36	-0.372	-0.231	-0.294
0.2	69	69	69	69	3.31	3.36	3.36	3.41	-0.538	-0.62	-0.529	-0.548	-0.52	-0.448	-0.261	-0.32
0.3	103.5	103.5	103.5	103.5	3.08	3.17	3.17	3.22	-0.477	-0.52	-0.498	-0.527	-0.38	-0.526	-0.328	-0.478
0.4	138	138	138	138	2.89	2.94	2.99	2.99	-0.455	-0.47	-0.49	-0.478	-0.48	-0.431	-0.524	-0.403
0.5	172.5	172.5	172.5	172.5	2.7	2.7	2.74	2.74	-0.461	-0.43	-0.452	-0.447	-0.7	-0.445	-0.489	-0.428
0.6	207	207	207	207	2.46	2.51	2.51	2.56	-0.429	-0.45	-0.432	-0.463	-0.63	-0.614	-0.491	-0.616
0.7	241.5	241.5	241.5	241.5	2.25	2.25	2.96	2.3	-0.451	-0.42	-0.734	-0.497	-0.81	-0.558	0.218	-1.022
0.8	276	276	276	276	2.03	2.08	2.08	2.13	-0.452	-0.46	-0.444	-0.474	-0.8	-0.743	-0.587	-0.7

The results of no geometric defects under C2 working condition are shown in Table 15 below.

Table 15 Calculation results under C2 working condition without geometric defect amplitude

Initial stress	Initial stress value (MPa)	Ultimate bearing capacity factor	Mid-span sinking value	Mid-span lateral offset
0	0	5.39	-1.822	0
0.1	35.5	4.81	-1.832	0
0.2	69.5	4.77	-1.840	0
0.3	104.5	4.68	-1.832	0
0.4	139	4.50	-1.821	0
0.5	173.5	4.45	-1.837	0
0.6	208	4.37	-1.827	0
0.7	242.5	4.28	-1.820	0
0.8	0	3.90	-1.822	0

The results of L/5000 defects under C2 working condition are shown in Table 16 below.

Table 16 Calculation results under L/5000 geometric defect amplitude under C2 working condition

Initial stress L/5000/4000/3000/2000	Initial stress value (MPa)				Ultimate bearing capacity factor				Mid-span sinking value				Mid-span lateral offset			
	L/2000	L/3000	L/4000	L/5000	L/2000	L/3000	L/4000	L/5000	L/2000	L/3000	L/4000	L/5000	L/2000	L/3000	L/4000	L/5000
0	0	0	0	0	3.63	3.68	3.74	3.79	-0.612	-0.61	-0.621	-0.638	0.416	0.28	0.266	0.306
0.1	34.5	34.5	34.5	34.5	3.47	3.5	3.55	3.6	-0.576	-0.57	-0.575	-0.589	0.439	0.278	0.253	0.294
0.2	69	69	69	69	3.27	3.31	3.36	3.41	-0.526	-0.53	-0.534	-0.551	0.392	0.303	0.276	0.313
0.3	103.5	103.5	103.5	103.5	3.08	3.13	3.17	3.22	-0.491	-0.49	-0.501	-0.524	0.419	0.334	0.319	0.396
0.4	138	138	138	138	2.89	2.94	2.99	2.99	-0.47	-0.47	-0.49	-0.476	0.492	0.416	0.455	0.352
0.5	172.5	172.5	172.5	172.5	2.65	2.7	2.74	2.74	-0.434	-0.44	-0.454	-0.444	0.478	0.426	0.443	0.37
0.6	207	207	207	207	2.46	2.51	2.51	2.55	-0.458	-0.46	-0.438	-0.501	0.653	0.615	0.481	0.736
0.7	241.5	241.5	241.5	241.5	2.2	2.25	2.3	2.3	-0.431	-0.44	-0.51	-0.443	0.614	0.576	0.854	0.524
0.8	276	276	276	276	1.98	2.03	2.08	2.08	-0.439	-0.44	-0.46	-0.444	0.662	0.606	0.62	0.53

Through the comparative analysis of data under different geometric defect distributions, the comparison shown in the figure below is obtained. From the figure, we can see that the ultimate bearing capacity is the highest when there is no defect in the three geometric defect conditions. Big. For A2 geometric defect condition, when the defect amplitude is L/5000, its ultimate bearing capacity coefficient. It's not that the greater the initial stress, the greater the coefficient. It decreases first, then rises a little, then falls, then rises and falls when the amplitude of geometric defects increases, the ultimate load-carrying capacity coefficient basically increases with the initial stress

Increase and decrease, the larger the defect amplitude, the smaller the ultimate bearing capacity coefficient.

Figure 21 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficients of different initial stress degrees under A2 working condition

Figure 22 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficients of different initial stress degrees under B2 working condition

Figure 23 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficients of different initial stresses under C2 working condition

Through the comparative analysis of the data under the same geometric defect amplitude and stress should be controlled within 0.4. The geometric defect amplitude should be controlled within L/5000, and the initial stress should be controlled within close to 0.4.

Figure 22 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficient of different working conditions under L/5000 geometric defect amplitude

Figure 23 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficient of different working conditions under L/4000 geometric defect amplitude

Figure 24 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficient of different working conditions under L/3000 geometric defect amplitude.

Figure 25 Ultimate bearing capacity coefficient different working conditions under L/2000 geometric defect amplitude.

5-Conclusions

The concept of the initial stress degree and the influence coefficient of the ultimate bearing capacity is defined, ultimate bearing capacity of the CFST arch bridge at a certain degree showed that the ultimate bearing capacity reduction caused by the initial stress is not more than 12% is the limit, and it needs to be controlled so that the initial stress not increase greater than 0.5.

The influence of different parameters the analysis results showed that the larger the slenderness ratio, the greater the effect on the bearing capacity with initial stress; according to the ultimate bearing capacity coefficients obtained at different steel content ratios, it can be known that the greater the steel content ratio, the higher the ultimate bearing capacity coefficient, the ultimate bearing capacity coefficient under 9%-14% steel content is compared with 8% steel content the growth rate of the ultimate load-carrying capacity coefficient is between 0-18%. The higher the steel content, from the comparison of the ultimate bearing capacity coefficients of the four steel types, it is found that compared with Q235, the other three steel types the growth rate of the ultimate bearing capacity coefficient under is 12%-24%, the higher the strength of the steel, the ultimate stable bearing capacity the greater the force coefficient; the growth rate under C50 from the two concrete grades C60 and C55 is up to 11.3%. It can be seen that the concrete grade has a relatively small influence on the ultimate bearing capacity of the concrete-filled steel tube arch bridge.

The distribution and size of the initial defects are analyzed: the initial defect amplitude is selected as L/2000 and L/3000, L/4000, L/5000 four cases, the distribution position is selected according to the buckling mode of the arch bridge including six ways to arrange defects in and out of the plane.

The in-plane and out-of-plane of the CFST arch bridge and the comprehensive consideration of initial stress and out-of-plane limit bearing the influence of the load force results show that the amplitude of geometric defects is controlled within L/5000, and the initial stress is controlled within 0.4 within a reasonable range.

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7- Data Availability

Data used to support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon request.

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